

The La^{III} complexes are as usual diamagnetic, while all other lanthanum complexes are paramagnetic. The comparison of these observed values with those observed for 8-hydrated sulphates⁸ and those calculated for uncomplexed ion⁴, indicates that the 4f-electrons do not participate in bonding in these complexes.

The S=O stretching frequency in the ir spectra of free DBzSO appears as a strong band^{5,6} at 1 032 cm^{-1} , while it shifted to 965–950 cm^{-1} in the spectra of its complexes, generally appearing as a very strong broad band. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band of free DBzSO appearing at 682 cm^{-1} undergoes a slight positive shift on complexation. A negative shift of $\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ and a positive shift of the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ are indicative of the decrease in the double bond character of the S=O bond and an electron shift from the aryl group to the sulphur atom of the ligand. The data thus suggest coordination through the oxygen atom to the ligand. A very strong absorption attributed to phenyl-S stretch by previous workers⁷ has been identified at 1 079 cm^{-1} in free DBzSO which does not undergo any significant change on complexation. It may be taken as an indication of the absence of coordination from the sulphur atom of the ligand. The $\nu_{\text{Ln-O}}$ band appeared in the region 400–360 cm^{-1} .

In the nitrate complexes, the occurrence of two strong bands at 1 525–1 510 and 1 310–1 290 cm^{-1} region is attributed to ν_4 and ν_1 modes of the vibration of covalently bonded nitrate group, respectively, suggesting that the nitrate groups lie inside the coordination sphere^{9,10}. The nature of binding of the nitrate group can be predicted by examining^{10,11} the combination bands in the region 1 800–1 700 cm^{-1} . A separation of 55–30 cm^{-1} in the combination bands suggests a bidentate nitrate coordination.

The thermal studies reveal that the complexes start losing mass (above 200°) with partial loss of the DBzSO ligand. A loss of 49.18–50.26% is observed in the range 200–320°, corresponding to the loss of 2.7 moles of the ligand. A further loss of 73.12–74.36% correspond to the complete loss of the ligand molecules. The residue obtained at about 780° corresponds to Ln_2O_3 .

In the bromide complexes the lanthanide ions are linked by three Br^- ions and five oxygen atoms of DBzSO, resulting in eight-coordination. The NO_3^- groups are bidentate in the nitrate complexes, $\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 4\text{DBzSO}$. Linking of Ln^{III} with 6 nitrate oxygen and 4 DBzSO oxygen results ten-coordination of lanthanum(III) in these complexes.

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Studies on Samarium(III) Complexes with some Substituted-dibenzoylmethanes at 0.1 M Ionic Strength and Apparent Molar Volume of 2'-Hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane in Mixed Solvents

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THE formation constants of La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} chelates with substituted sulphonic acids in aqueous medium have been studied by Narwade¹. Sherry *et al.*² investigated the lanthanide complexes with carboxylic acids. Ramamoorthy and Manning studied exhaustively the mixed ligand chelates of mesoditartaric acid with divalent and trivalent metals³. Darnall and Birnbaum⁴ showed that a lanthanide ion could substitute for calcium ion and produce an active enzyme system⁴. The present work is aimed to investigate the complexing ability of 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane, 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-methoxydibenzoylmethane and 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane with samarium(III) ion. Millerio *et al.*⁵ determined solvation numbers for amino acids in aqueous solutions and in some cases in pure methanol and ethanol⁵. We have also undertaken a study of the apparent molar volume of 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane (1.1×10^{-3} M) in different dioxane-water mixtures.

Experimental

All the chemicals including sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid were of AnalaR grade. 2'-Hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane and 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane were prepared following the literature method⁶. All the ligands were crystallised and their purity was checked by repeated crystallisation before use. Since ligands were insoluble in water, the solutions of the purified ligands were prepared in 75% dioxane-water mixture and standardised potentiometrically. Samarium perchlorate was prepared in the laboratory from samarium oxide (B.D.H.). pH measurements were carried out on a Elico LI-120 digital pH-meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit at 27° and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO₄). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen gas through an assembly containing the electrodes in order to keep away CO₂. The *B* values (pH-meter readings in dioxane-water mixtures) were converted to (H⁺) values by applying the corrections proposed by Van Uitert and Fernelius⁷.

The spectrophotometric measurements were made with a 'AMIL Spectrochem.' Elico spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand formation constants: The deviation of the (acid+ligand) curves from the acid curves started around pH 2.5 and remained constant upto pH 7.0 and then further increased continuously upto pH 11.00 (Fig. 1). The deviation increases after pH 7.0, which may be due to the dissociation of OH group of the ligand. The average numbers of protons associated with the ligand ($\bar{n}_A$) were determined by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁸. Formation curves were obtained by plotting values of $\bar{n}_A$ against pH of the system. The values of *p*k (dissociation constants of the OH groups) were evaluated by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$, and accurate values were also determined by pointwise calculations. The values of *p*k obtained from the ligands are presented in Table 1. The *p*k values are found to decrease due to the effect of electron-withdrawing groups.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The departure of the (acid+ligand+metal) titration curves from the (acid+ligand) titration curves was around pH 3.0 in 75% dioxane-water mixture (Fig. 1). It clearly indicated that the commencement of complex formation between metal ion and ligand started from pH 3.0. The values of $\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation number) were calculated by Irving and Rossotti expression⁸. The values of log *K*₁ (stability constant for 1 : 1 complex) were obtained from the plots of $\bar{n}$ vs *P*_L. The values of log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ were calculated by half-integral method from the formation curves using the known values of *P*₁ at which $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5, respectively, and by the method

Fig. 1. Plots of pH vs volume of NaOH; $\mu = 0.1$ M, Sm^{III}-2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND (*p*k) AND METAL-LIGAND (log *K*) STABILITY CONSTANTS

Ionic strength = 0.1 M			
System	<i>p</i> k	log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ₂
Sm ^{III} -2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane	10.55	12.26	10.06
Sm ^{III} -2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-methoxydibenzoylmethane	9.65	11.60	9.56
Sm ^{III} -2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane	8.90	10.23	8.54

of pointwise calculations. The values of log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ obtained for all the three systems are given in Table 1. The proton-ligand stability constants (*p*k values) and metal-ligand stability constants (log *K* values) could be utilised to verify the validity of log *K* = (*a* *p*k + *b*) relation⁹ found by many workers to hold good for transition metal ion complexes of a series of closely related ligands. Plots of log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ vs *p*k have been observed in our present investigation to show a fairly good linear relation, giving slope values 1.0 and 1.2, respectively. Jones and Vertak¹⁰ suggested on the basis of purely electrostatic model that the slope

will increase with increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation. The observed slope value is higher than those of the transition metal complexes.

Spectrophotometry. Method of isobestic points: McBryde¹¹ investigated the interactions between Fe^{III} ion and 1,2-dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonic acid in aqueous medium by the spectrophotometric technique. Sm^{III}-2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane system was studied in the present investigation spectrophotometrically. Absorption curves at different pH for the solution containing samarium perchlorate (1.0×10^{-2} M) and the ligand (20×10^{-2} M) were constructed (Fig. 2). The absorption curves intersect at one point at 585 nm (isobestic point) indicating the presence of two different complex species (1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes) in the pH range 2.0–6.0.

Fig. 2. Plots of absorption vs wavelength: pH (1) 2.0, (2) 2.5, (3) 3.5, (4) 4.1, (5) 4.6, (6) 5.5 and (7) 6.0; $\mu = 0.1$ M, Sm^{III}-2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane, isobestic point at 585 nm.

The colour of solution was light brown below pH 3.0 and dark brown above 3.0. The change in colour of the solution at different pH values indicates the formation of complexes between Sm^{III} ion and 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane.

Apparent molar volume: Jahagirdar and Pankanti^{1,2} studied the apparent molar volumes and adiabatic compressibility of 1-amino acids in mixed solvents. Apparent molar volumes of 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane in different percentage of dioxane-water mixtures have been studied in the present investigation (Table 2). It is observed that the apparent molar volume decreases continuously with increasing percentage of the organic solvent (i.e. decreasing dielectric constant). This may be due to electrostriction which can be related to the number of water molecules (nH) associated with the ligand. The plot between apparent molar volume and mole fraction

of dioxane shows linear relationship. The same linear relationship was also observed by Jahagirdar and Pankanti^{1,2}.

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES $\phi(v)$ OF 2'-HYDROXY-3,4-BENZO-4-NITRODIBENZOYL METHANE IN DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE OF DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Dioxane-Water %	d_0 g cm ⁻³	d g cm ⁻³	$\phi(v)^*$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
70	1.0440	1.0426	1701.00
75	1.0424	1.0412	1474.48
80	1.0414	1.0405	1187.82
85	1.0400	1.0395	804.80
90	1.0378	1.0374	710.15

$$*\phi(v) = \frac{1000}{C} - \frac{1}{d_0} \left(\frac{1000d}{C} - M \right)$$

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Solid State Degradation of Carbamide in Presence of Tin Oxides

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IN continuation of our earlier work on solid state decomposition to correlate solid state chemistry and catalysis and to tailor catalysts to meet specific demands^{1,2}, we presently report on the solid state degradation of carbamide in presence of tin oxide samples of different origins.